

CATTLE DOMESTICATION REVISITED: MIDDLE NILE EVIDENCE SUGGESTS INDEPENDENT ORIGINS IN AFRICA 10,000 YEARS AGO

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ABSTRACT

New zooarchaeological discoveries in the Middle Nile support the scenario that proto-pastoralist communities arrived from the sub-Saharan region with large ruminants at the beginning of the Holocene. Until now, it has been accepted that domesticated cattle arrived in Africa in 6,000 BCE from the Middle East. New osteometric data from Letti Desert 2 (LTD2) in Sudan analysed through point-scale method as well as age-profile suggest that cattle could have been domesticated independently in Africa at the same time as in the Middle East, that is around 10,000 years ago.

Introduction

Although cattle were domesticated slightly later than sheep and goats (e.g. Zeder 2017), they seem to be extremely important species in the history of mankind in Eurasia and especially in Africa. One of the fundamental tasks facing archaeozoology is to gain an understanding of the processes of animal domestication. Those engaged in this field of study perceive animal domestication in a much broader context than a mere change in diet (Bogaard et al. 2021). They consider the factors that drove humans to take up this new form of relationship with animals to be both environmental, social and resulting from cultural evolution (Cauvin et al. 1998; Helmer et al. 1998; 2005). Currently, the oldest archaeozoological evidence of domestication of the wild ancestor of cattle - the aurochs (*Bos primigenius*) comes from middle Euphrates and is dated to 10-9 ka BCE (Helmer et al. 2005). The identification of the wild ancestor, the aurochs, from domesticated cattle is relatively straightforward, based on the change in body proportions and, above all, the reduction in size with the disappearance of sexual dimorphism. However, the identification of animals in the early stages of domestication is a highly complex task that requires multi-faceted contextual studies. Such studies must take into account a number of natural factors, including climatic changes, the hunting impact, and those resulting from herding, such as selection. Although studies employing statistical analyses of osteometric data or age-of-death profiles are beset with significant shortcomings, they have proved invaluable for identifying the early stages of domestication. This is particularly the case when changes in sexual dimorphism in cattle in western Asia are under consideration (Helmer et al. 2005). Nevertheless, this kind of comprehensive research and examination of morphological alterations within early cattle populations is only feasible in the Middle East, where access to extensive archaeozoological collections and a multitude of chronologically and ecologically consistent sites is far greater than in the Nile Valley.

Genetic studies also play a pivotal role in the cattle domestication debate. The prevailing theory suggests that cattle around the world are descendants of a small population of aurochs domesticated around 11,000 years ago in the Middle Euphrates zone (Bollongino et al. 2012; Pitt et al. 2019). From there, via Sinai, at the turn of 7/6 millennium BCE, cattle and other domesticated animals, such as sheep, goats, and pigs, are thought to have spread across Africa (Fig.1; Stock and Gifford-Gonzalez 2013). Thus, the prevailing view currently encountered in academic discourse is that the domestication of animals in Asia, Europe, and Africa was a homogenous process "invented" in the Middle East, from where the *know-how* or the animals themselves spread with humans.

Half a century ago, based on discoveries made in the Southwest of Egypt (Nabta Playa in Western Desert), a hypothesis was proposed about the possibility of local cattle domestication in Africa (Gautier 1987). Although it was supported by ecological, archaeological (Jórdeczka et al. 2013), linguistic (Ehret 1993), and some genetic evidence (Bradley et al. 1996), the hypothesis was poorly supported by direct osteological data. The very early dating (9-8 millennium BCE) of the Nabta Playa sites, the lack of conclusive, statistically significant osteological data, and the generally limited state of research on early Holocene settlement in North Africa led to the rejection of the idea of domestication of cattle in Africa (MacDonald 2000; Brass 2018).

Figure 1 – Hypothesized and dominant in current discourse main domestication zone and migration routes of taurine (*Bos taurus*) cattle, including postulated domestication zone in Western Desert, based on genomic research (Pitt et al. 2019). Underlay: DEM (Greyscale Shaded Relief, ASTER, Terra, <https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov>)

Intensive genetic research conducted in the early 21st century additionally ruled out the domestication of cattle in Africa (Bollongino et al. 2012), even though it was assumed for a long time that the African aurochs (*Bos primigenius opistonomus/africanus*) influenced the

genotype of modern African cattle (Perez-Pardal et al. 2010; Larson and Fuller 2014; Kim et al. 2023). Due to natural conditions (high temperatures, extremely dry climate), ancient DNA from African aurochs and an early form of domestic cattle has been very difficult to obtain and analysed to a very limited extent. The first and the only genomic data to date from a single aurochs from 9,000 years ago comes from Morocco (Verdugo et al. 2019). The earliest autosomal genomes and mitogenomes of African domestic cattle come from bones dated between 2,800 and 2,000 years ago (Ginja et al. 2023), but it should be noted that positive genetic results are usually only obtained from 300 (!) year old remains. Research is therefore almost exclusively based on modern genetic material or fossil data from outside Africa.

Today, nearly 500 million people around the globe sustain themselves through itinerant pastoralism; half of them are Africans (Manzano et al. 2021). The emergence of cattle herding in Africa marked a key moment in the continent's history. Pastoral communities with complex social systems are perceived as the main element that initiated the emergence of the oldest civilisations in the Northeast of Africa (Hanotte et al. 2002; Di Lernia 2006). Also today, a complex system of herding fundamentally affects the economy, society, and demography of sub-Saharan and East Africa (Hatfield and Davies 2006). Yet, in the academic discourse to date, the picture of Neolithic communities focused on crop cultivation and sedentary farming has placed herding on the margins of the global debate about neolithisation and the origins of the process of animal domestication (Salvatori and Usai 2019).

In this article, we revisit the thesis that cattle domestication took place in Africa at the same time as in the Middle East and that African pastoralism could have a native origin (e.g. Barich 2016), supporting it with new zooarchaeological findings. A key element is the data from Letti Desert 2 (LTD2) site in North Sudan, published in details for the first time and dated with a consistent series of radiocarbon dating to the mid- 8th millennium BCE (Fig.2, 4). Due to the very limited collection of osteological and osteometric data, the findings from Letti cannot provide a final proof for the local domestication of cattle in Africa. They are circumstantial evidence and a factor which suggests that we should not close the debate and continue our archaeozoological and archaeological research to test the hypothesis that independently of the Middle East, communities may have taken steps to control wild cattle herds in order to secure access to meat or perhaps other benefits.

Figure 2 - Location of archaeological sites mentioned in the text. Orange – Early Holocene, blue – middle Holocene (Neolithic), gray – Kerma/Kush. Underlay: DEM (Color Shaded Relief, Aster, Terra, <https://earthdata.nasa.gov>)

LETTI DESERT 2 site and osteological collection

The LTD2 site was discovered in 2022 during surface surveys in the Letti Basin, Middle Nile (Osypinski et al. 2022b). It is located on an elevation that is part of the edge of a plateau overlooking one of the ancient watersheds of the Nile. During two field seasons, the work focused on the trench designated LTD2/A (10x5m). Three stratigraphic horizons were distinguished at this site. The clusters of human bones found on the surface were identified as relics of burials eroded by deflation. We assume that the burials were a part of Neolithic cemetery with its core area excavated by about 180 meters to the east (LTD2/B – Fig.3C). The radiocarbon dating of these remains indicates inhumation in the 5th or 4th millennium BCE (Osypinski et al. 2023, tab.3). Therefore, we should assume that the current surface layer in area

LTD2/A includes remains of settlements from the early Holocene and relics of later activities (isolated fragments of pottery, stone tools and deflated burials). For this reason, in further analysis, materials from this horizon (i.e. from Loci 1 and 2) are treated as contaminated, although containing early-Holocene materials (cattle remains including).

The most important bone materials discussed in this paper come from subsurface layers and cut features (Loci 3-5) of 0.5m thickness in total (Fig.3B). In these layers we found numerous fragments of technologically and typologically homogeneous ceramics ornamented with alternate pivoting stamp, lithic artifacts dominated by the cutting inserts of composite tools, and mineralized animal remains (Table 1). Ostrich eggshell (OES) beads and a small clay zoomorphic figurine were manifestations of non-utilitarian art (Osypinski et al. 2022b). The assemblage of cultural artifacts from the Early Holocene settlement of LTD2 differs significantly from the most abundantly recorded collections from Mesolithic sites in the region. Radiocarbon dating of ostrich egg pieces found at each level (surface including) indicate, in most cases, that the 8th millennium BCE was a period of at least several phases of settlement (Fig.4). Two samples (Poz-164652, Poz-164653) suggest a more recent chronology (turn of the 7th and 6th millennia BCE). However, these last results were obtained from the analysis of carbonate fractions of dentin and enamel from cattle (none of these samples were burnt). Therefore, they may reflect the age of secondary processes (recrystallisation) long after the death of the organism.

Meanwhile, the deepest horizon - Locus 6 was a layer of rock debris combined with silt, which formed the natural substrate in the early Holocene. It still contained a trace amount of early Holocene relics (lithics, single potsherds).

Figure 3 – site LTD2/A: A – subsurface features (4a- 4c) containing early-Holocene (EH) remains, cutting Locus 3 (deposition layer also rich in EH materials); B – S section with marked surface (yellow) and homogenous EH loci (shades of brown); C – DEM of the site and location of explored areas LTD2/A and LTD2/B (Neolithic cemetery core area)

Figure 4 – Radiocarbon dating of Early Holocene materials from LTD2/A. Color markings: yellow shadow – surface finds; red - burnt fragments of OES, gray - unburned fragments of OES, green - cattle dentine (carbonate fractions). Layout – OES fragments and beads from LTD2/A.

Archaeozoological analysis

We analyzed a total of 2402 animal remains, including invertebrates and vertebrates, using archaeozoological methods (Table 1, Gifford-Gonzales 2018; Lasota-Moskalewska 2008).

Figure 5 – Preservation of animal remains from LTD2/A

The remains were well-preserved (Fig. 5), wherever coming from the current surface (Loci 1-2) or subsurface levels (Loci 3-5) with fragmentation primarily resulting from anthropogenic activities. Thus, we assume the whole collection of animal remains is homogenous and came from early-Holocene settlement (what is confirmed by coherent OES dating).

Table 1. Animal remains from area LTD2/A (complete data after 2022 and 2023 seasons). Number of remains from the current surface in brackets.

TAXONS	NISP	%NISP	MNI
Molluscs		23.41	
Nile oyster (<i>Etheria nilotica</i>)	141 [5]	18.67	95
Pila (<i>Pila ovata</i>)	33 [2]	4.37	32
Cypraeidae sp.	1 [0]	0.13	1
FISH		13.37	
Fish (Pisces sp.)	72 [27]	9.53	2
Nile tilapia (<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>)	9 [0]	1.19	1
Siluriformes sp.	19 [0]	2.51	1
REPTILES		0.13	
Nile monitor (<i>Varanus niloticus</i>)	1 [0]		1
BIRDS		21.06	1
Common ostrich (<i>Struthio camelus</i>) – egg shell	159 [27]		
MAMMALS		42.40	
Dipodillus sp.	1 [0]	0.13	1
Cape hare (<i>Lepus capensis</i>)	3 [1]	0.40	1
Crested porcupine (<i>Hystrix cristata</i>)	2 [0]	0.26	1
Aardvark (<i>Orycteropus afer</i>)	5 [0]	0.66	1
Caninae sp.	3 [0]	0.40	1
Black-backed jackal (<i>Lupulella mesomelas</i>)	2 [2]	0.26	1
Suidae sp.	1 [0]	0.13	1
Common warthog (<i>Phacochoerus africanus</i>)	63 [36]	8.34	2
Cattle (<i>Bos primigenius</i>)	61 [28]	8.08	3
Dik-dik (<i>Madoqua saltiana</i>)	18 [5]	2.38	1
Oribi (<i>Ourebia ourebi</i>)	67 [24]	8.87	2
Bohor reedbuck (<i>Redunca redunca</i>)	8 [0]	1.06	1
Waterbuck (<i>Kobus ellipsiprymnus</i>)	86 [26]	11.40	4
NISP TOTAL	755	31.43	
Large Size Mammal	41 [0]		
Large Size Ruminant	27 [11]		
Middle Size Mammal	49 [30]		
Middle Size Ruminant	152 [28]		
Small Size Mammal	33 [0]		
Small Size Ruminant	41 [4]		

Mammal	890	
	[505]	
Unidentified	403 [78]	
TOTAL	2 391	100

The bones were partially mineralized and have a thin layer of calcite on their surface. Animal remains were subject to taxonomic and anatomical identification as well as the identification of the size class, body sides, and body parts. They were also assessed in terms of age at death, sex, and morphological characteristics of the animals.

Where the necessary morphological characteristics were preserved, osteometric data were collected according to standardised protocol (Von den Driessch 1976). The NISP classification, the minimum number of elements, and the standardised minimum number of animal units (%MAU) were used to estimate the quantification methods (Binford 1984; Grayson 1984; Lyman 1994). The remains from LTD2/A displayed an advanced level of mineralization, which caused the ZooMS and DNA analyses to fail. Various statistical methods adapted for the analysis of morphological and osteometric data are being used in archaeozoology, the most popular is the LSI scaling technique (Pöllath and Peters, 2005). However, due to limited cattle metric data set from LTD2, with no measurements homogeneity (longitudinal, latitudinal, anatomically diverse), we chose the point scale method (e.g. Lasota-Moskalewska 2005), which has been successfully used for three decades in studies in Central Europe, the Middle East and NE Africa (e.g. Osypińska et al. 2021b; 2022a; Osypińska 2024b). It allows us to use all the bone measurements we obtained for comparison. The method is described in details below (sections Archaeozoological analysis/Morphological analysis).

Cattle from Letti

In terms of morphology and size, the cattle discovered at LTD2 correspond to indigenous African cattle (Grigson 2000). These were large primigenic cattle (c. 130-150cm WH). The osteometric data for cattle from LTD2/A that we registered (Table 2) fit well within the ranges of metric data for domestic cattle both from Neolithic (Wadi Khashab, 5th mill. BCE: Osypinski et al 2021b) and ancient Kerma (3rd -2nd mill. BCE: Chaix 2011) sites (Fig. 7).

Table 2 – Osteometric values of remains of *Bos* from LTD2/A. Age determination: A – adult, SA – subadult, Y – juvenile. The finds from a current surface marked in italics.

Locus	Bone	Osteometry (mm)
2023/13 – Loc.3	Mandible	M2: L-26.76; B-24.22 (A)
2023/20 – Loc.4a	Mandible	M3: L-42.75; B-16.82 (A)
2023/13 – Loc.3	Mandible	M3: L-40.59; B-17.11 (A)
2023/10 – Loc.3	Scapula	GLP-78.26; SLC-57.35 (A)
2023/20 – Loc.4a	Humerus	Bd-84.22; BT-74.45 (A)
<i>2023/27 – Loc.2</i>	<i>Metacarpus III</i>	<i>Bd-16.63; 16.78 (A)</i>
<i>2023/27 – Loc.2</i>	<i>Metacarpus IV</i>	<i>Bd-17.35 (A)</i>
2023/11 – Loc.3	Pelvis	LA-79.23 (A)
<i>2023/27 – Loc.2</i>	<i>Tibia</i>	<i>Bd-63.57 (A)</i>
<i>2023/27 – Loc.2</i>	<i>Talus</i>	<i>GLI-65.84 GLm-60.78 Bd-40.08 (SA)</i> <i>GLI-43.83 GLm-40.43 Bd-28.82 (Y)</i>
2023/14 – Loc.4	Metatarsus III+IV	Bp-58.96 (A)
2023/13 – Loc.3	Phalanx I	Bd-19.32 (SA)
2023/19 – Loc.4	Phalanx III (anterior)	DLS-85.28; Ld-68.60 (A)
<i>2023/27 – Loc.2</i>	<i>Phalanx III</i>	<i>DLS-43.27 Ld38.42 (Y)</i> <i>DLS-46.53 Ld-42.47 (Y)</i> <i>DLS-48.89 Ld-40.54 (Y)</i>

Figure 6 – Cattle remains discovered at site LTD2/A compared to bones of aurochs (green) and ancient domestic cattle (red) from Middle Nile region. A: lower molar M3 (LTD2/A) and mandible of ancient cattle (c.2000 BC); B: juxtaposition of metatarsal epiphyses from left: aurochs, LTD2/A cattle, ancient cattle and medieval cattle; C: talus (ancient cattle and LTD2/A); D: distal phalange (anterior); E: remains of juvenile cattle from LTD2A (metatarsal epiphyses, fragments of proximal phalanges, talus and distal phalanges (anterior and posterior)).

The dimensions of the bones and teeth of the cattle in LTD2 fit into the medium-large range of dimensions of cattle from NE Africa. However, they are clearly larger than the dimensions of *taurine* cattle, that we observe in some Neolithic deposits and much later local cattle populations (Kush and medieval: [Osypińska et al. 2022a](#)). The bones of cattle from LTD2 are also partly similar to the size of aurochs bones in the region ([Linseele 2004](#); [Osypińska et al. 2021a](#)), which may be due to the strong sexual dimorphism in the aurochs. This feature has

so far contributed to the difficulty of unequivocally identifying cattle domestication in archaeozoological studies in Africa, although in-depth analyses of morphological features in terms of sexual dimorphism in the Middle East have been successful in identifying the early stages of cattle domestication (Helmer et al. 2005). We have identified cattle remains based on characteristic details in the skeleton (Peters 1986), and comparative collections. The identification of cattle (*Bos*) in this case is not in doubt, not least because the only morphologically similar bovid species - the buffalo (*Syncerus caffer*) - is not reported in Early Holocene faunal material in the Middle Nile Valley (Peters 1989a, 1989b; Chaix and Honegger 2014), but is recorded southerly, in central Sudan (e.g. Khor Shambat site - Dunne et al. 2021). Detailed analyses of buffalo ecology highlight that it was more adapted to the forests and savannas of sub-Saharan Africa, suggesting that its geographical range rarely included the Nile Valley (Prins et al. 2023). Discoveries of relatively rich collections of aurochs remains at Late Pleistocene sites in the Middle Nile Valley (Osypińska et al. 2021a) attest to the southern range of this species, much further than previously assumed (Linseele 2004). The identification of domesticated cattle features is much more problematic. Due to the availability of osteometric data, it was possible to compile a summary considering metric data of Pleistocene and Holocene aurochs from the Nile Valley, and rich collections of undoubted domesticated cattle from NE African sites dated to 5-1 ka BCE. It was therefore necessary to support our studies with other proxies. The age-at-death profile for cattle from LTD2 provides such support. Cattle was the only group of animals from LTD2 in which we find the remains of very young (around 6 months) and immature (3-4 years) individuals together with the remains of mature individuals (Table 3; Fig. 6). The remains of all other wildlife species (antelopes, warthogs, porcupines, etc.) were exclusively from mature individuals. Herd reduction through the elimination of redundant juveniles: males and females after calving, is considered one of the primary markers of ruminant domestication (Zeder 2008).

Figure 7. A - Summarized osteometric data of LTD2 cattle – remains of adult animals only (n=11), African Aurochs (n=57: Affad [Osypinska et al. 2021a], Buto [von den Driesch 1997], Merimde [von den Driesch and Boessenck 1985], Tell Ibrahim Awad [Boessenck, J. and von den Driesch 1992], Fayum [Gautier 1976]) and early NE-African domestic cattle (Neolithic Sudan n=158; Wadi Khashab n=108; Kerma n=2795) using the points method; B - ranges of osteometric data of African Aurochs and domestic cattle after transposition into the African cattle point scales, with medians (cattle figurines) indicated.

TEN THOUSAND YEARS OF “CATTLE CENTRED” SOCIETIES IN NE AFRICA

Over 10,000 years ago, groups of people returned to the Middle Nile after millennia of a late-Pleistocene settlement hiatus (Kuper and Kröpelin 2006). They settled in LTD2, among other places. Their return coincided with dynamic climate changes involving the northward shift of the monsoon range and the savannah zone (de Menocal et al. 2000). According to our findings based on environmental studies, the behavior of these communities was related to the exploitation of the Sudan Savannah Zone ecosystem. Animals of the *Bos* genus arrived in the Nile Valley the same way. They, along with the local antelope and warthog species, were one of the main sources of meat for humans (Table 3). However, they were the only animals to be killed at various ages, also when young. A behavioral/settlement link with natural pasture ecosystems for herds of herbivores and particularly with the cattle lead us to identify these groups as proto-pastoralists. The term ‘proto-pastoralist’ appears in a variety of research contexts, particularly related to the transition from hunter-gatherer communities to more structured forms of herd management (e.g. Betts and Helms 1987). It can be posited that an intensification of interspecies relations was occurring, though this still did give a limited alterations in the cultural system (Kristiansen et al. 2023) and, on the second side, in animal morphology. It would be inaccurate to characterise the Early Holocene communities of Letti as

pastoralists (Makarewicz 2013; Manzano et al. 2021), but we do see features of nomadism in them and a close association with herds of (wild?) cattle.

Table 3. Representation of identified mammals in the Early Holocene osteological collection from LTD2/A (NISP=674) according to ecological niches occupied (Kingdon et al. 2013), *SSR* – small size ruminants, *SSM* – small size mammals, *MSR* – medium size ruminants, *MSM* – medium size mammals, *LSR* – large size ruminants, *LSM* – large size mammals

CLASS	WEIGHT RANGE	%	SPECIES	Age of deth	Habitat
I	Small <20 kg 	4.2%	Hare, Jackal, Dik-dik Porcupine	Adult 100%	Grasslands/Sahel/savannas Semi-desert/grasslands/savannas Semi-desert/ woodland/grassland savannas
II	Small-medium 20-100 kg 	32.3%	Oribi, Bohor reedbuck Warthog, Aardvark, SSR, SSM	Adult 100%	Grasslands, woodlands, >500mm a. rainfall Savanna grasslands/bushlands/woodlands Open woodlands, sparse scrub, grassland
III	Large-medium 100-300 kg 	42.6%	Waterbuck, MSR, MSM	Adult 100%	Grasslands/savannas Riverine woodland/shrub/grasslands, 400-1600mm annual rainfall
IV	Large 300-1000 kg 	20.8%	Cattle, LSR, LSM	Adult: 85.5% Sub-adult: 8.7% Juveniles: 5.8%	Grasslands, open woodland

In the 7th millenium BCE, which was significantly later than the arrival of the **hypothetical** proto-pastoralists we have introduced to the debate, settled communities appeared in the region. The behaviour of these new communities was associated with the exploitation of exclusively wild elements of the aquatic and coastal environment, hence they were referred to as Mesolithic/Aqualithic in earlier publications (Haaland 1995). Both the proto-pastoralist communities and those described as Mesolithic were producing ceramic vessels, albeit representing markedly different traditions (Mesolithic “Karmakol” ware commonly tempered with chaff or mica (Gatto 2006) – absent in LTD2 assemblage).

The early Holocene communities appeared by the Nile in the region of the so-called Nile Great Bend where the three dry valleys connecting the Nile, Kordofan (Wadi el- Melik), and the Mega-Chad (Wadi Howar) zone converge. Throughout subsequent millennia, they served as excellent migration routes, providing seasonal access to resources, namely, plants and water (Jesse et al. 2013).

The communities of the 8th millennium BCE inhabited the Nile Valley selecting specific fertile areas, called “basins”, including Letti and Selima. This is evidenced by archaeological records from LTD2 and el-Barga (Honegger 2004) sites. These are regions in which, in a slightly later period (6-5 millennium BCE), the formation of increasingly large necropolises, e.g. R12 (Usai and Salvatori 2008), Kadruka (Chaix and Reinold 2018) was observed.

The feature linking the studied communities from the 8th and 5th, as well as the 3rd millennium BCE is the significant role of cattle in the economy, symbolism, and burial practices. From 2,000 BCE these animals were widely replaced with significantly smaller *taurine* cattle in the Middle Nile area (Olivieri et al. 2015). Due to progressing climate and environmental changes, since the 3rd millennium BCE, there has been a shift of pastoral communities (Sawchuk et al. 2018), in which cattle were used in many areas of ritual, social, and economic life, away from the Nile and further to the South.

Beef was the staple of the diet of religious and social elites also in later periods of Nubia's history, even though environmental conditions were unfavourable to breeding cattle locally (desertification). The analysis of strontium isotopes in cattle from sites of the Kush civilisation (1,000 BCE - 350 CE) and later – up to the post-medieval times, provides clear evidence that a significant part of the population originated outside of the Nile Valley (Osypinska et al. 2022a).

AFRICAN WAY TO CATTLE DOMESTICATION

New paleontological and archaeological discoveries indicate that the relationship between humans and cattle in Africa has a much longer history than previously assumed. One hypothesis suggests that the remains of Pleistocene aurochs discovered in North Africa are usually associated with Acheulean sites (1.7 – 0.13 Mya) and migrations of the *Homo erectus* towards Europe (Martínez-Navarro et al. 2014). Discoveries from the Middle Nile Valley indicate that

at the time of our species *Out of Africa*, c. 50 kya (MIS3) the area was inhabited by communities that seasonally specialised in hunting aurochs (Osypińska et al. 2021a).

The results of our research led us to propose a thesis that at the time of the last drastic aridification (MIS2) in Central Africa refugial areas for the savannah ecosystem were preserved, e.g., in the Mega-Chad and Kordofan zones (Fig. 8). Finds of aurochs remains from Kashm el-Girba dating to over 8,000 BCE support this assumption (Peters 1989b). Hunting specialisation, recorded in the late Pleistocene (Osypińska et al. 2021a), was hypothetically conducive to controlling herds of select animals, to following them, and to protecting them (theses already proposed at the dawn of modern science although since the mid-20th century superseded by the concept of the Neolithic Revolution). They could constitute a "living resource" and a safety net in emergency situations. This set of human behaviours could consequently promoted the transition to the early stage of domestication, without strong interference from behavioural, morphological, and physiological changes in the animals, as was the case in the Middle East. In the early Holocene, when the savannah extended to the Southern Sahara once again (Nicoll 2004), people and the cattle previously isolated in the central part of Sahel migrated to the Nile Valley.

Figure 8 - Sites in NE Africa with *Bos* remains (including doubted Nabta Playa and Kerma/el-Barga) and their hypothetical sources of origin (ellipses) and routes (arrows) into the Nile Valley. The colors of the site icons reflect chronological diversity: yellow - Terminal Pleistocene (>9700 BCE), orange - Early Holocene (9700-6200 BCE), blue - Middle Holocene (6200-2200

BCE). The change in the extent of the summer Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) between the Late Glacial Maximum (LGM: 24-18 millennium BCE) and the African Humid Period (AHP: 12-3 millennium BCE) reflects a significant ecological change (Junginger et al. 2014). Map source: ESRI Shaded Relief.

The zooarchaeological criteria commonly used to identify the local domestication of a species on the basis of morphology based on the frequency of occurrence of the remains of the wild ancestor in the osteological material; the so-called 'intermediate form' and the remains of animals showing signs of domestication (e.g. reduced size, altered proportions, lack of horns - e.g. Caramelli 2006; Peters et al. 2013). The large reduction in size of the animals could have been caused, in addition to ecological factors, either by hunting selection (Helmer et al. 2005), by a drastic change in the diet of the domesticated animals, and by natural or deliberate selection (Zeder 2006). This direction of morphological change was favourable for agricultural communities living in dense settlements, such as those typical of the Fertile Crescent (Manning et al. 2015). African cattle populations, may have been subject to a different model of evolution, because of the different model of pastoralism has developed in sub-Saharan Africa, namely nomadic pastoralism. In this model, under the ecologically favourable conditions of the early Holocene, there may not have been drastic changes in the diet and behaviour of animals compared to their wild ancestors, nor in their morphology as a result of deliberate selection. Consequently, there are no factors that could cause rapid and very pronounced morphological changes, such as a reduction in body size or proportions. This is supported by zooarchaeological and osteometric data. The size of African aurochs corresponds in part to that of early cattle (Chaix 2007; Grigson 2000). Of course, both archaeozoological (Pöllath and Peters 2005) and ethnographic (Gifford-Gonzalez 1998) data suggest that a marked reduction in size of cattle in pastoralists herds can also be observed, but this is more likely to apply to assemblages much younger than the 8th millennium BCE. As can be seen, the application of identification criteria based on morphological traits, as defined for studies in the Middle East, cannot provide satisfactory results in Africa. If these criteria are applied, only the *taurine* cattle from Southwest Asia, which appeared by the Nile only in the 6th millennium BCE, can be recognised as "fully" domesticated.

Conclusion

The relatively poor state of research on early Holocene settlements in sub-Saharan Africa, the paucity of zooarchaeological data and the application of research criteria developed for Southwest Asia and Europe have had a serious impact on the existing picture of African prehistory. The correlated zooarchaeological, archaeological and chronological data from the Middle Nile that we have presented may provide a rationale for reopening the debate on the possible independent domestication of cattle in Africa at the beginning of the Holocene. It is essential to continually enrich the state of research in these studies and to acquire faunal collections, which are extremely modest compared to those available in the Middle East. Only on the basis of rich osteological collections will it be possible to imply statistical methods enabling the identification of the initial stages of domestication. Unfortunately, due to the current political situation in sub-Saharan Africa, there is a serious risk that for a long time, academia will not have an archaeozoological database adequate to that of the Fertile Crescent. Our article on the discoveries from Letti in Sudan aims to present data that are intended to provide a rationale for sustain the debate on the hypothesis of the African genesis of domestic cattle.

We put forward the thesis that 10,000 years ago communities, with their own ceramic traditions and the savannah-dependent subsistence, arrived in the Middle Nile from the central Sahel. The migration was correlated with the climate optimum of the "Green Sahara" (MIS1). The communities arrived with cattle whose morphological characteristics and age profile suggest evolved inter-species relationship that hypothetically could reflect an early stage of domestication. Temporary settlements were established in the Nile Valley in regions with the most favourable conditions for grazing, preferred in subsequent periods by Neolithic and later pastoralists. The migration of "proto-pastoralists" with cattle to the Middle Nile and the domestication of ruminants in the Fertile Crescent occurred at approximately the same time.

Archaeozoological sampling

The early Holocene animal remains analysed in this study come from research carried out in cooperation between the National Corporation for Archaeology and Museums in Khartoum, the Institute of Archaeology and Ethnology at the Polish Academy of Sciences, and the University of Wrocław. Based on the contract and formal permissions, teeth for strontium isotope analysis were transported to Adam Mickiewicz University Foundation in Poznań for cleaning and measurement. Other fragments of animal bones and teeth are stored in the archaeozoological lab at the Archaeological Studies Centre in Banganarti, North Sudan.

Archaeozoological analysis

Where possible, animal remains were subject to taxonomic and anatomical identification as well as the identification of the size class, body sides, and body parts. They were also assessed in terms of age at death, sex, and morphological characteristics of the animals. Their age was assessed based on the observation of the stage of ontogenetic development of the teeth and bones. These concerned the degree of fusion of the long bone diaphysis with the epiphysis (Kolda 1936; Chaplin 1971; Grigson 1982; Schmid 1972; Silver 1970; Reitz 2008; Amorosi 1989). An alternative method used to determine the age of animals consisted of the analysis of the development of their teeth (Lutnicki 1972; Müller 1973). Based on this data, the percentages of remains of morphologically immature animals were calculated, accepting the number of remains of a given species in successive separate sets, as 100%. Based on the evaluation of the materials in terms of the age profile at the time of slaughter of animals of a given species (cattle), we were able to identify two groups represented by morphologically immature animals. The first group consisted of very young animals (*juvenis*) and the second of adolescent animals (*sub-adult*). The latter identifies individuals that, despite characteristics indicating morphological immaturity (e.g. incomplete permanent dentition and incomplete ossification of the skeleton), have already achieved dimensions of adults or dimensions close to these.

Where the necessary morphological characteristics were preserved, osteometric data were collected according to standardised procedures (Von den Driesch 1976). The identification was made based on reference collections held at the Archaeozoological Lab at the Archaeological Studies Centre in Banganarti. For analysis of anatomical distributions, the method of technological division of the carcass was applied according to the following categories: head (skull, mandible, teeth, horns); thorax (vertebrae, sternum, ribs), proximal part of the thoracic limb (scapula, humerus, ulna, radius); distal part of the thoracic limb (carpal bone, metacarpal bone), proximal part of the pelvic limb (pelvic bone, femur, patella, tibia); distal part of the pelvic limb (talus, calcaneus, tarsal bone, metatarsals), phalanges (I, II and III phalanges). The NISP classification, the minimum number of elements, and the standardised minimum number of animal units (%MAU) were used to estimate the number of identified elements. To estimate the MNE, body sides, anatomical location, and age of each identifiable specimen were evaluated.

Morphological analysis

In the studies of the morphology of cattle population, the points scale method modernised for the purposes of archaeozoological studies was used along with the statistical procedure for data coding originally expressed in the formula:

$$Y_i = [(X_i - X_{\min}) / (X_{\max} - X_{\min})] 100\%,$$

where Y_i stands for the encoded measurement of a given characteristic in a given individual i ; X_i stands for the empirical measurement of the characteristic in a given individual i ; X_{\max} and X_{\min} stand for the maximum and minimum values of measurement of a given characteristic recorded in the entire data set (Manly and Navarro 1986; Kobryń and Lasota-Moskalewska 1989).

This procedure has been successfully applied in archaeozoological studies in Europe for three decades and in Northeast Africa for one decade ([Osypińska et al. 2021b](#); [Osypińska et al. 2022a](#)). It allows for the assessment of the obtained, unmeasured osteometric values relating even to single characteristics obtained from the bones, in a broader reference to the data on the characteristics of prehistoric animal populations ([Kobryń and Lasota-Moskalewska 1989](#); [Lasota-Moskalewska 1982-1984](#)).

Due to the specific character of the morphology of livestock from Africa, expressed in, among other things, long-leggedness, it became necessary to develop scales dedicated to African animal populations. Thus, for archaeozoological studies of populations from Sudan and Egypt, separate point scales appropriate to the study of livestock populations from this region of Africa were created. To create scales for the studies of cattle, a total of about 20,000 osteometric data were collected both from African aurochs and from cattle from all stages of prehistory and historical times in the Nile Valley, Eastern Desert, and Western Desert, up until modern times. All available osteometric data from dozens of archaeological sites in Egypt and Sudan were used to create scales for Eastern African populations ([Osypińska 2018](#)).

Data availability

All data used in this study have been included in the article. Additional data related to this paper are available open-access (ZENODO: [Osypińska 2024a](#); [Osypińska 2024b](#)) and may be requested from the authors. Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to the authors.

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Author contributions

P.O. conceived and designed the project. M.O. analyzed the bone sample, performed the statistical analysis. M.O. and P.O. interpreted the data, wrote the manuscript. P.W. and R.Ł. provided maps and plans. M.Ch., P.B., M.C., J.K and H.M. were members of team involved

in Letti sites exploration. All authors have read and contributed to the document and all approve of its submission to this journal.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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